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STABILITY INDICATING METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF SOFOSBUVIR, VELPATASAVIR AND VOXILAPREVIR IN A PHARMACEUTICAL FORMULATION BY UHPLC

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ABSTRACT

A Precise, accurate, Robust, Rugged, Specific, Stability indicating RP-UHPLC method has been developed and validated for the estimation of anti viral drugs Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir in pharmaceutical dosage form (Tablets) was carried out on Agilent UHPLC with Acquity BEH C18 (50 x 3.0mm, 1.7 μ m) column with mobile phase contains 0.05% Orthophosphoric acid: Acetonitrile: Methanol (40:40:20) at a flow rate of 1.0mL/min, detection was carried out at 270nm. The retention time of the Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir 2.04, 3.50 & 5.37mins respectively. The method produces linear responses in the range of 200 μ g/mL to 600 μ g/mL for Sofosbuvir, 50 μ g/mL to 150 μ g/mL for Velpatasavir, 50 μ g/mL to 150 μ g/mL for Voxilaprevir with correlation coefficients (r^2 1.00), The % Recoveries between 100.5 to 101.7 for Sofosbuvir, 99.0 to 99.9 for Velpatasavir and 100.3 to 101.1 for Voxilaprevir. Peak purity was more than 0.999 of main peaks in all forced degraded samples.

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INTRODUCTION

Sofosbuvir is a direct acting antiviral medication used as part of combination therapy to treat chronic Hepatitis C, an infectious liver disease caused by infection with Hepatitis C Virus (HCV). HCV is a single-stranded RNA virus that is categorized into nine distinct genotypes, with genotype 1 being the most common in the United States, and affecting 72% of all chronic HCV patients.

Figure-01: Structure of Sofosbuvir.

Sofosbuvir is nucleotide analog inhibitor, which specifically inhibits HCV NS5B (non-structural protein 5B) RNA-dependent RNA polymerase. Following intracellular metabolism to form the pharmacologically active uridine analog triphosphate (GS-461203), sofosbuvir incorporates into HCV RNA by the NS5B polymerase and acts as a chain terminator. More specifically, Sofosbuvir prevents HCV viral replication by binding to the two Mg²⁺ ions present in HCV NS5B polymerase's GDD active site motif and preventing further replication of HCV genetic material.

Velpatasavir is a Direct-Acting Antiviral (DAA) medication used as part of combination therapy to treat chronic Hepatitis C, an infectious liver disease caused by infection with Hepatitis C Virus (HCV). HCV is a single-stranded RNA virus that is categorized into nine distinct genotypes, with genotype 1 being the most common in the United States, and affecting 72% of all chronic HCV patients.

Figure-02: Structure of Velpatasavir.

Velpatasavir mechanism of action is likely similar to other selective NS5A inhibitors which bind domain I of NS5A consisting of amino acids. NS5A inhibitors compete with RNA for binding at this site. It is also thought that NS5A inhibitors bind the target during its action in replication when the binding site is exposed. Inhibition of NS5A is also known to produce redistribution of the protein to lipid droplets. The exact role of NS5A in RNA replication is not yet understood although it is known to be an important component.

Voxilaprevir is a Direct-Acting Antiviral (DAA) medication used as part of combination therapy to treat chronic Hepatitis C, an infectious liver disease caused by infection with Hepatitis C Virus (HCV). HCV is a single-stranded RNA virus that is categorized into nine distinct genotypes, with genotype 1 being the most common in the United States, and affecting 72% of all chronic HCV patients.

Figure-03: Structure of Voxilaprevir.

Voxilaprevir exerts its antiviral action by reversibly binding and inhibiting the NS3/4A serine protease of Hepatitis C Virus (HCV). Following viral replication of HCV genetic material and translation into a single polypeptide, Nonstructural Protein 3 (NS3) and its activating cofactor Nonstructural Protein 4A (NS4A) are responsible for cleaving genetic material into the following structural and nonstructural proteins required for assembly into mature virus: NS3, NS4A, NS4B, NS5A, and NS5B. By inhibiting viral protease NS3/4A, voxilaprevir therefore prevents viral replication and function.

A Survey of literature reveals that analysis of the Sofosbuvir and Velpatasavir include only RP-HPLC methods. The UHPLC Simultaneous determination of Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir not has at been quantified to the best of knowledge. In this Research we developed a chromatographic method and validated the separation of three anti-viral drugs present in the fixed pharmaceutical dosage form.

Experimental:

Chemicals & Reagents:

Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir are obtained as kind of gifted samples from Chandra laboratory Pvt. Ltd. Orthophosphoric acid, Methanol, Acetonitrile and Milli-Q Water(UHPLC Grade) were obtained from Merck, Mumbai, India. Formulation product VOSEVI® Tablets contains Sofosbuvir –400mg, Velpatasavir –100mg and Voxilaprevir -100mg obtained from Gilead Sciences, kaulalampur, Malaysia.

Equipment and Chromatographic conditions:

Agilent 1290 Infinity Equipped with PDA Detector with EZ Chrome software. This UHPLC System contains Column Oven and Auto sampler Temperature control and an online degasser. Acquity BEH C18 (50*3.0mm, 1.7µm) column is used as stationary phase for separation. An Isocratic mode used for the separation of components from the mixture. Mobile phase consisting of 0.05% Orthophosphoric acid: Acetonitrile: Methanol (40:40:20) at a flow rate of 1.0mL/min, the detection was carried out at 270nm, Column Oven Temperature 40°C, Auto sampler Temperature 25°C and Injection volume 10µL. 0.05% v/v Orthophosphoric acid prepared in water by adding 0.5mL of Orthophosphoric acid to 1000mL of water. Then mixed and degassed in the ratio of 40:40:20 with 0.05% Orthophosphoric acid: Acetonitrile: Methanol.

Method Development & Validation:

After several trials by changing the ratios of buffer and organic solvents, buffer compositions, buffer concentrations and different columns, finally required separation, peak shapes achieved by 0.05% Orthophosphoric acid: Acetonitrile: Methanol (40:40:20) at a flow rate of 1.0mL/min with Acquity BEH C18 (50*3.0mm, 1.7µm) column.

All three analytes were prepared 10µg/mL concentration in methanol individually. Scanned in the UV-Visible spectrometer, all drugs were overlaid and determined isobestic point at 270nm (Figure No-04).

Figure No-04:UV graph Overlay for Sofosbuvir, Velpatasvir and Voxilaprevir.

Standard solution preparation:

Standard stock solution of the 3 active ingredients of the drug taken was prepared in the following manner, Transfer Accurately about Sofosbuvir 400mg, Velpatasvir 100mg and Voxilaprevir 100mg of working standards into a 200mL volumetric flask, dissolve and dilute with mobile phase. 5mL of this solution further diluted in 25mL with mobile phase. Mix well.

Test solution preparation:

Accurately taken twenty tablets, taken average weight, Then crushed in the mortar and pestle homogeneously and a quantity equivalent to one tablets was weighed and transferred in to 200mL of volumetric flask, added 160mL of diluent(Mobile phase) and sonicated for 30min by intermittent shaking. After 30min made the final volume with diluent. This test solution centrifuged at 5000RPM for 10min. Taken clear layer 5mL from test solution transferred in a 25mL volumetric flask. Volume made with diluent, mixed well. Filtered final solution through 0.45 μ m PVDF Syringe Filter with 3mL discarded volume.

Specificity:

Preparation of Placebo solution:

A quantity 400mg (equivalent to one tablets without active ingredients) was weighed and transferred in to 200mL of volumetric flask, added 160mL of diluent(Mobile phase) and sonicated for 30min by intermittent shaking. After 30min made the final volume with diluent. This solution centrifuged at 5000RPM for 10min. Taken clear layer 5mL from solution transferred in a 25mL volumetric flask. Volume made with diluent, mixed well. Filtered final solution through 0.45 μ m PVDF Syringe Filter with 3mL discarded volume. Injected in to chromatographic system. The respective chromatogram fig no:6 shows the no peak interference with sample analytes.

Acceptance criteria:

Placebo should not show any interference at the retention time of the main peaks.

System suitability:

The system suitability assessed by five replication of the drugs at concentration of 400 μ g/mL Sofosbuvir, 100 μ g/mL Velpatasvir and 100 μ g/mL Voxilaprevir.

Acceptance criteria:

% RSD Should be ≤ 2.0 for the peak area of the individual components. The system suitability parameters with respect to theoretical plates, tailing factor and resolution between the peaks were defined. The results are tabulated in table no:2 and the typical chromatogram is shown in fig no:5.

Linearity:

Linearity of the method was evaluated at five equi-spaced concentrations by diluting the standard stock solution to give solution over the range 50-150% target of all three analytes respectively. Calibration curve was constructed at 5 concentrations of Sofosbuvir(200,320,400,480 & 600 μ g/mL), Velpatasvir(50,80,100,120 & 150 μ g/mL) and Voxilaprevir (50,80,100,120 & 150 μ g/mL) , these were injected in to chromatographic system, plotted a graph concentration versus area to evaluate correlation coefficient. The linearity data and calibration curves are shown in table no: 3 and fig no: 7,8,9 respectively.

Acceptance criteria:

Correlation coefficient should not be less than 0.99.

Method Precision:

The method precision was investigated using six individual sample preparations as reported above. Six preparations were injected individually in to chromatographic system & Calculated % Assay of individual samples. Acceptance criteria of % Assay should be 95.0 to 105.0 & Acceptance criteria of % RSD for six preparations assay values should be ≤ 2.0 . The results and the Method Precision chromatogram are listed in table no:4 and fig no:10 respectively.

Accuracy & Recovery:

Accuracy of the method was determined by measuring with analytes in the presence of placebo. Accuracy solutions prepared in to three level (50%, 100% and 150%). For each level the preparations were prepared individually. 50%, 100% & 150% Solutions were prepared with different drug weights with constant weight of placebo in the manner of sample preparation. Concentrations of Sofosbuvir (200, 400, & 600 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), Velpatasavir (50,100& 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and Voxilaprevir (50,100& 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Acceptance criteria of % Recovery should be 98.0 to 102.0 the results are shown in table no:5.

Acceptance criteria:

% RSD for nine preparations recover values should be ≤ 2.0 .

Robustness:

To determine the Robustness of the developed method, experimental conditions were deliberately changed and %RSD for Replicate injections of standard solution (400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Sofosbuvir, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Velpatasavir and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Voxilaprevir) peak areas, theoretical plates, tailing factor and resolution were evaluated. The mobile phase flow rate was changed to 0.8mL/min & 1.2mL/min (Actual flow rate: 1.0mL/min) and the robustness data and chromatograms were shown in table no:8,9 and fig no: 11,12 respectively.

Acceptance Criteria:

System suitability should be within the acceptance criteria.

Intermediate Precision (Ruggedness):

Intermediate precision (also called within-laboratory or within-device) is a measure of precision under a defined set of conditions, same measurement procedure, same measuring system, same location, and replicate measurements on the same or similar objects over an extended period of time. The Intermediate Precision (Ruggedness) was investigated using six individual sample preparations as reported above. Six preparations were injected individually in to chromatographic system & Calculated % Assay of individual samples. Acceptance criteria of % Assay should be 95.0 to 105.0, % RSD for six preparations assay values should be ≤ 2.0 & % RSD for Method precision and Intermediate Precision assay mean values Should be ≤ 2.0 and the results were tabulated in table no:6.

Analysis of the pharmaceutical formulation:

Weighed accurately 20 tablets and calculate the mean weight after they are finely powdered in motor and pestle. Equivalent weight of 1 tablet (606mg) was taken in 100ml volumetric flask and mix with diluent by the process of sonication and filtration through 0.45 μm filter paper. Take 50ml volumetric flask and add the filtrate of 5ml and make with the diluent. Amount of Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir in the pharmaceutical marketed formulation by the relative linear calibration equation. The assay results data were shown in table no: 10.

Forced degradation studies:

The specificity of the method can be demonstrate through forced degradation studies conducted using the acid, alkaline, oxidation, thermal and photo stability conditions and the data is indicated in table no:1 and 7.

Table 01: Conditions for the stress degradation study of Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir.

Condition	Test Samples Treated with
Hydrolysis by Acid	2mL of 5N Hydrochloric acid for 2Hrs at room temperature, then neutralized with 2ml of 5N Sodium hydroxide solution
Hydrolysis by Base	2mL of 5N Sodium hydroxide for 2Hrs at room temperature, then neutralized with 2ml of 5N Hydrochloric acid solution
Oxidation by Peroxide	2mL of 30% of H_2O_2 for 2Hrs at room temperature
Thermal Degradation	Tablets were exposed to 105°C for 2Hrs
Photolytic Degradation	Tablets were places in photolytic chamber up to achieve 1.2million lux hrs.

Acceptance Criteria:

Main Peaks Peak purity should be more than 0.999.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:**System suitability:****Figure 05: System suitability chromatogram of Standard solution.**

Parameter	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir
Retention Time in min	2.04	3.45	5.38
Theoretical plates	15457	21541	23221
Tailing Factor	1.1	1.3	1.2
Resolution	---	3.5	4.5
Area	83035155	24022758	28970525
%RSD	0.2	0.3	0.3

Table 02: Results of System suitability study

From the above results of %RSD, theoretical plates, tailing factor and Resolution were obtained within acceptance criteria.

Specificity:**Figure 06: Typical Chromatogram of Placebo solution.**

From the above chromatogram placebo was not interfered at retention time of main peaks were obtained so method is specific.

Linearity:**Table 03: Linearity data results of Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir.**

Parameter	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir
Concentration Range($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	200.06 to 600.18	50.07 to 150.21	50.09 to 150.27
Regression equation	$y=21198.92x+235960$	$Y=24217.02x+5773.10$	$Y=29411.59x+10391.30$
Slope(m)	21198.92	24217.02	29411.59
Intercept(c)	235960	5773.10	10391.30
Correlation	1.00	1.00	1.0
Coefficient(r^2)			

Figure 07, 08& 09: Calibration curves of Sofosbuvir, Velpatasvir and Voxilaprevir standard solutions.

From the above results correlation coefficient of three analytes were not less than 0.99 so the method is linear.

Method Precision:

Figure 10: Method Precision chromatogram for Test solution.

Table No-04: Method Precision data for Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir.

Sample Name (% Assay)	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir
Method Precision_01	99.7	99.0	100.0
Method Precision_02	100.0	98.5	99.5
Method Precision_03	99.8	98.8	99.4
Method Precision_04	99.1	98.7	99.3
Method Precision_05	98.8	98.0	99.2
Method Precision_06	99.0	98.2	99.4
Average	99.4	98.5	99.5
%RSD	0.5	0.4	0.3

From the above results were within the acceptance criteria, % Assay results obtained 95.0 to 105.0% and % RSD was less than 2.0 so the method is precise.

Accuracy and Recovery:

Table No-05: Accuracy and Recovery data for Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir.

Parameter	Amount added ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	%Recovery	%RSD
Sofosbuvir: 50% Level,	215.17	216.25	100.5	0.6
100% Level,	411.20	419.20	101.7	
150% Level	629.40	638.14	101.4	
Velpatasavir: 50% Level,	51.56	51.05	99.0	0.5
100% Level,	100.89	100.40	99.5	
150% Level	153.61	153.46	99.9	
Voxilaprevir: 50% Level,	52.38	52.55	100.3	0.4
100% Level,	101.07	102.11	101.0	
150% Level	154.61	156.24	101.1	

From the above results %Recovery obtained within the acceptance criteria (98.0 to 102.0%), %RSD also obtained less than 2.0. so method is accurate.

Intermediate Precision (Ruggedness):

Table No-06: Intermediate Precision data for Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir.

Sample Name (%Assay)	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir
Intermediate Precision_01	99.4	99.0	97.3
Intermediate Precision_02	99.2	98.9	99.7
Intermediate Precision_03	99.3	99.1	97.7
Intermediate Precision_04	101.0	99.9	99.3
Intermediate Precision_05	102.6	97.4	102.3
Intermediate Precision_06	99.3	99.0	98.4
Average	100.1	98.9	99.1
%RSD	1.4	0.8	1.8
%RSD Between Day-01 & Day -02 Assay Results	0.5	0.3	0.2

From the above results were within the acceptance criteria, % Assay results obtained 95.0 to 105.0% and % RSD was less than 2.0, %RSD of Day-01 & Day-02 Assay Results less than 2.0%, so method is Rugged.

Forced degradation study results:**Table No-07: Forced degradation studies data for Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir.**

Condition	%Assay			Peak Purity		
	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir
Acid Hydrolysis	98.6	98.1	98.2	0.999925	0.999985	0.999961
Alkaline Hydrolysis	98.5	97.5	99.5	0.999911	0.999991	0.999995
Oxidation	98.7	98.0	99.6	0.999941	0.999952	0.999952
Thermal	98.1	97.6	98.7	0.999985	0.999998	0.999984
Photolytic	99.5	98.8	99.8	0.999221	0.999955	0.999251

From the above results were within the acceptance criteria, because peak purity of the main peaks were more than 0.999 so method is specific and stability indicating.

Robustness:**Decreased Flow rate 0.8mL/min:****Figure 11: Standard solution chromatogram for decreased flow rate (0.8mL/min).****Table No-08: Robustness data for decreased Flow rate (0.8mL/min).**

Parameter	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir
Retention Time in min	2.55	4.34	6.70
Theoretical plates	15525	21841	23741
Tailing Factor	1.1	1.3	1.2
Resolution	---	3.6	4.6
%RSD	0.3	0.5	0.6

Increased Flow rate 1.2mL/min:**Figure 12: Standard solution chromatogram for increased flow rate (1.2mL/min).**

Table No-09: Robustness data for increased Flow rate (1.2mL/min).

Parameter	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir
Retention Time in min	1.70	2.91	4.51
Theoretical plates	16008	21958	24012
Tailing Factor	1.1	1.3	1.2
Resolution	---	3.5	4.4
%RSD	0.7	0.3	0.8

From the above results system suitability results were within the acceptance criteria, so method is Robust.

Table No:10 Assay results of Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir.

Formulation	Label Claim(mg/tablet)			Amount Found(mg)		
	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir	Sofosbuvir	Velpatasavir	Voxilaprevir
Vosevi ®	400 mg	100 mg	100 mg	399.55 mg	101.15 mg	100 mg

CONCLUSION

In this study, a validated simple, specific and reliable UHPLC method was described for the estimation of a Pharmaceutical Formulation (Tablets) consisting of Sofosbuvir, Velpatasavir and Voxilaprevir for oral administration. All the three active ingredients were successfully resolved and quantified using Agilent UHPLC with Acquity BEH C18 (50 x 3.0mm, 1.7µm) column in a relatively short run time of 10 minutes in Isocratic mode of the chromatographic system. The proposed method provides a good resolution between active ingredients. The developed method reported herein was validated by parameters as described in the ICH Q2B guideline they are system suitability, specificity, linearity, method precision, accuracy, robustness and ruggedness. The proposed method has the advantages of repeatability, sensitivity and requires less expensive reagents. This method is also used for estimation of stability samples because it was found that there is no interference in forced degradation studies, so this is stability indicating method for future research.

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Conflict of interest :

Nil

Abbreviations:

UHPLC	: Ultra High Performance Liquid Chromatography
RPC	: Reversed Phase Chromatography
ICH	: International Conference on Harmonization
UV	: Ultra violet spectroscopy
SD	: Standard Deviation
%RSD	: Percentage Relative Standard Deviation
M.P	: Mobile Phase
mg	: milligrams
mm	: millimeter
µm	: Micrometer
µg	: Microgram
ml	: Milliliters
%	: Percentage
v/v	: volume/volume
N	: Normality
µg/ml	: micrograms per milliliter
n	: Retention Time
mins	: Minutes
ppm	: Parts per million
Psi	: Pascals Per Square inch
API	: Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
NLT	: Not Less than
NMT	: Not More than
BEH	: Ethylene Bridged Hybrid

HCV	: Hepatitis C Virus
RNA	: Ribose Nucleic Acid
DAA	: Direct-Acting Antiviral
PVDF	: Polyvinyl Difluoride
PDA	: Photo diode array
hrs	: Hours

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